

Atrial Fibrillation in Patients with Transient Ischemic Attack in Accordance with the Tissue-Based Definition

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Abstract

Background—Transient ischemic attack (TIA) management requires a cardiac evaluation with a Holter electrocardiogram (ECG), preferably a long-term (24 h) electrocardiogram (LT-ECG), to detect atrial fibrillation (AF), which places patients at higher risk of cerebrovascular events. The aim of this study was to determine the frequency of AF using ECG and LT-ECG in patients with tissue-based TIA.

Methods—During a three-year period (starting in 2011), all consecutive patients with tissue-based TIA (no evidence of infarction by brain imaging) were included and prospectively evaluated.

Results—Of 861 patients (mean age, 70 ± 13 years; 49.7% women), 854 patients (99.2%) had an ECG at admission, and 338 patients (39.3%) underwent 24-h LT-ECG monitoring during hospitalization. Patients who underwent LT-ECG monitoring were significantly younger (68 vs. 71 years; $P=0.001$) and experienced longer symptom duration (143 vs. 79 minutes; $P=0.024$) compared with those who did not. Furthermore, they had lower rates of unilateral weakness (32% vs. 39%; $P=0.034$) and previous strokes (18% vs. 26%; $P=0.007$). The LT-ECG investigation was also associated with longer hospitalization (7.9 vs. 5.7 days; $P<0.001$). A total of 77 patients (8.9%) exhibited AF on the ECG at admission. The LT-ECG revealed AF among seven patients (2.1%); five of these received a new treatment with oral anticoagulation based on the LT-ECG findings. Using the logistic regression, the presence of AF was associated with the following: age over 65 years (odds ratio [OR], 20.6; 95% confidence interval [CI], 2.8–152; $P=0.003$), hypertension (OR, 3.1; 95% CI: 1–8.9; $P=0.041$) and increased glucose level >6.05 mmol/L on admission (OR, 1.9; 95% CI: 1–3.5; $P=0.036$).

Conclusion—Cardiac evaluation with LT-ECG appears to increase the rate of detected AF and may lead to a change in secondary prophylaxis in patients with tissue-based TIA.

Keywords

Atrial fibrillation; cardioembolism; outcome; stroke; TIA; tissue-based definition

INTRODUCTION

Transient ischemic attack (TIA) is a common neurovascular event that is associated with a higher risk of stroke after the first event [1,2]. The definition of this term has recently been altered, and it is now defined by the American Heart Association as “a transient episode of neurological dysfunction caused by focal brain, spinal cord, or retinal ischemia, without acute infarction.” Cardioembolic pathology, such as atrial fibrillation (AF), is present in approximately 15% to 20% of patients with cerebrovascular events [3,4]. The presence of AF leads

to more severe strokes and greatly increases the risk of stroke [5]. Because most strokes occur during a two-day time interval after a TIA [6], it is important to identify TIA etiology and initiate therapy as quickly as possible so as to prevent patients from suffering a disabling stroke.

Even though guidelines recommend that an electrocardiogram (ECG) should be performed on admission to hospital and that a long-term electrocardiogram (LT-

Table 1. Comparison between patients who were underwent an LT-ECG during hospitalization versus those who not.

Baseline characteristics	Long-term ECG (24 h)		P value
	Yes (n=338)	No (n=523)	
Male sex	263 (50)	170 (50)	.9
Mean age, years (SD)	71.2 (13.7)	68.2 (12.2)	.001
Age > 65 years	372 (71)	216 (64)	.03
TIA symptoms			
Amaurosis fugax	28 (5.5)	14 (4.2)	.4
Facial paralysis	100 (19)	58 (17)	.8
Dysarthria	102 (20)	53 (16)	.1
Aphasia	116 (22)	76 (23)	.9
Unilateral motor weakness	206 (39)	109 (32)	.03
Sensibility loss	166 (32)	123 (37)	.2
Mean symptoms duration, minutes	79 (248)	143 (337)	.02
Medical history			
Hypertension	405 (77)	246 (73)	.2
Hypercholesterolemia	160 (31)	119 (36)	.1
Myocardial infarction	31 (5.9)	24 (7.2)	.5
Diabetes mellitus	105 (20)	87 (26)	.05
Previous stroke	136 (26)	61 (18)	.007
Premedication			
Statin	153 (31)	92 (28)	.5
Antiplatelets	195 (39)	123 (37)	.7
Oral anticoagulation	93 (18)	6 (2)	< .001
Hospital stay, days (SD)	7.9 (2.6)	5.7 (3.1)	< .001
Stroke risk	3 (0.6)	2 (0.6)	.9
Re-TIA	9 (1.7)	13 (3.8)	.054

Data are in n (%) unless otherwise indicated.

ECG) should be performed during hospitalization as part of the diagnostic evaluation of patients with TIA [7], analyses of data obtained with Holter ECGs performed on patients with TIA in accordance with the new tissue-based definition do not exist. Most studies investigate groups of TIA and stroke patients together, with the patients with TIA comprising relatively small cohorts. In addition, the redefinition of TIA may mean that results obtained before the redefinition differ from those obtained following the redefinition. Furthermore, new studies show that longer electrocardiographic monitoring reveals occult AF more often than does regular LT-ECG monitoring [8–12].

The aim of this study was to determine ECG and LT-ECG (24 h) findings and associated factors of AF among unselected patients with TIA.

METHODS

Study design

During a three-year period (2011–2013), all consecutive patients suffering from TIA in accordance with the tissue-based definition [13] (i.e., without evidence of infarction by brain imaging) were included and prospectively evaluated in this monocenter study conducted in the Department of Neurology at the University of Lübeck, Germany. The data collection was part of the stroke registry in the Department of Neurology at our university hospital. To be included in this study, the patients had to exhibit transient neurologic symptoms

caused by an ischemia of the central nervous system (CNS), have no acute infarct evidence in the neuroimaging, and be 18 years or older. Patients were excluded from this study if they were admitted with a suspected TIA but were diagnosed after evaluation with other neurological conditions (e.g., migraine attack, epileptic seizure, functional disorder) during hospitalization. Patients who presented with TIA to the emergency department but declined hospitalization for TIA management were also excluded.

Data on the baseline and sociodemographic characteristics—age, gender, medical history, TIA symptoms, and secondary prophylaxes—were collected from the patients' medical files (Table 1).

Statistical analysis

We used the Statistical Product and Service Solutions software program (version, 22) to analyze the data. The data were described with mean and standard deviation values for continuous variables, absolute numbers, and percentages for categorical variables. A chi-square test was used to determine the correlation between categorical variables and a *t*-test between continuous variables. Adjusted logistic regression analysis was carried out to estimate the odds ratio (OR). All variables of clinical parameters with a *P* value less than 0.1 were entered into the logistic regression model. A *P* value less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Table 2. Comparison between patients with versus without atrial fibrillation detected during hospital stay

Characteristics	Atrial fibrillation		P-Value
	Yes (n=84)	No (n=770)	
Male sex	39 (46)	393 (51)	0.4
Mean age, years (SD)	80.1(8.5)	68.9 (13.2)	< 0.001
Age > 65 years	81 (96)	502 (65)	< 0.001
TIA symptoms			
Amaurosis fugax	3 (3.8)	37 (4.8)	0.9
Facial paralysis	21 (25)	136 (18)	0.08
Dysarthria	19 (23)	135 (18)	0.3
Aphasia	28 (33)	164 (21)	0.01
Unilateral motor weakness	40 (48)	274 (36)	0.03
Sensibility loss	16 (20)	271 (36)	0.007
Admission glucose (> 6.05mmol/L)	56(67)	383(51)	0.006
Medical history			
Hypertension	78 (93)	567 (74)	< 0.001
Hypercholesterolemia	29 (35)	247 (32)	0.6
Myocardial infarction	8 (9.5)	47 (6.1)	0.2
Diabetes mellitus	24 (29)	168 (22)	0.1
Previous stroke	32 (39)	162 (21)	< 0.001
Premedication			
Statins	36 (44)	207 (28)	0.003
Antiplatelets	31 (39)	285 (38)	0.9
Oral anticoagulation	40 (48)	57 (7)	< 0.001
In-hospital complications			
Any complication	26 (31)	87 (11)	< 0.001
Stroke	0 (0)	5 (0.6)	0.9
Re-TIA	4 (4.8)	17(2.2)	0.1
Medication at discharge			
Antihypertensive drugs	79 (94)	568 (74)	< 0.001
Antidiabetic drugs	19 (23)	127 (17)	0.2
Beta blockers	71 (85)	340 (44)	< 0.001
Statins	56 (67)	530 (69)	0.7
Antiplatelets	27 (33)	686 (89)	< 0.001
Oral anticoagulation	61 (73)	90 (12)	< 0.001
Hospital stay, days (SD)	6.1 (2.9)	6.6 (3.1)	0.1

Data are in n (%) unless otherwise indicated.

Results

A total of 861 patients (mean age, 70 ± 13 years; 49.7% women) fulfilled the inclusion criteria. An ECG on admission was performed on 854 patients (99.2%). On admission, 77 patients (8.9%) already showed AF on the ECG; for 15 of these 77 patients (19.5%), this diagnosis of AF was new. During hospitalization, a later ECG revealed AF in three more patients; for two of these three patients, this diagnosis was new.

Of the 861 patients included in this study, 338 patients (39.3%) underwent an LT-ECG during hospitalization. The patients who had an LT-ECG were significantly younger (68 years vs. 71 years; $P = 0.001$), had a longer symptom duration (143 minutes vs. 79 minutes; $P = 0.033$), a lower rate of pretreatment with oral anticoagulants (2% vs. 18%; $P < 0.001$) and stayed longer in hospital (7.9 days vs. 5.7 days; $P < 0.001$) than those who did not have an LT-ECG (Table 1). In addition, lower percentages of patients who had an LT-ECG had motor weakness as a TIA symptom (32% vs. 39%; $P = 0.034$) and a history of stroke than those who did not have an LT-ECG. The frequency of Re-TIA tended to be higher in patients who had an LT-ECG than in those who had not (3.8% vs. 1.7%, respectively; $P = 0.054$). The LT-ECG also revealed AF in seven patients (2.1%).

During hospitalization, AF was detected in 84 patients (9.8%), with 21 (25%) of these patients being diagnosed with AF for the first time.

As shown in Table 2, the patients with AF during hospitalization, as detected by ECG at admission or by LT-ECG, were significantly older than those without AF (80 years vs. 69 years, respectively; $P < 0.001$). In addition, higher percentages of patients with AF during hospitalization had unilateral motor weakness (48% vs. 36%; $P = 0.029$), aphasia (33% vs. 21%; $P = 0.012$), hypertension (93% vs. 74%; $P < 0.001$), and a history of stroke (39% vs. 21%; $P < 0.001$) than those without AF. However, a lower percentage of patients with AF during hospitalization had sensibility loss than those without AF (20% vs. 36%, respectively; $P = 0.006$). The logistic regression revealed an association between the presence of AF and the following: age over 65 years (odds ratio [OR], 20.6; 95% confidence interval [CI], 2.8–152; $P = 0.003$), hypertension (OR, 3.1; 95% CI: 1–8.9; $P = 0.041$), and glucose on admission higher than 6.05 mmol/L (OR, 1.9; 95% CI: 1–3.5; $P = 0.036$).

During hospitalization, a higher percentage of patients with detected AF developed more complications than those without detected AF (31% vs. 11%, respectively;

$P < 0.001$). The rate of patients receiving treatment with oral anticoagulation was also higher in patients with AF than in those without AF (73% vs. 12%, respectively; $P < 0.001$). The stroke risk and Re-TIA were similar in both groups (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

In the present study, almost all patients with TIA had an ECG on admission, and around 40% had an LT-ECG during their hospitalization as part of the TIA evaluation. The patients with TIA who had an LT-ECG were younger, had a longer symptom duration of TIA, and a lower rate of unilateral weakness as a symptom of TIA. Furthermore, the use of LT-ECG monitoring was associated with longer hospitalization, with these patients staying in hospital around two days longer on average.

The detection rate of AF when the ECG was performed at admission was 9% in the present study. When LT-ECG monitoring was performed during hospitalization in the present study, AF was detected in 2.1% of patients. These findings are similar to those of previous studies investigating the frequency of AF in patients suffering from cerebrovascular events, including TIA [11,14,15].

Logistic regression that included all patients who received LT-ECG and those who not, revealed correlations between AF and age > 65 years, the presence of hypertension at admission, and glucose level on admission > 6.05 mmol/L. Previous studies have also reported higher age, hypertension, and fasting glucose levels as risk factors (among others) for the development of AF [16,17]. However, in the present study, we measured the glucose level at admission, and we did not include the fasting glucose level in our protocol. Identifying patients with AF is important for the early prevention of subsequent stroke with oral anticoagulation. However, in our study, the stroke risk was generally low and similar to that found in a recent study investigating the stroke risk in hospitalized TIA patients [18]. However, in the present study, stroke risk was not increased in patients in whom AF was detected. This finding may be attributed to early TIA evaluation and immediate treatment with oral anticoagulation—particularly with the new direct oral anticoagulation, which produces earlier effects than anticoagulation with phenprocoumon, which needs several days to be optimized.

Our study has several limitations. One limitation is that not all patients underwent LT-ECG monitoring. Lastly, we did not differentiate between episodic and permanent AF.

Despite these limitations, our study has several strengths. To our best knowledge; it is the first study to investigate TIA in accordance with the definition for tissue-based TIA. Our study is also the first to investigate the frequency of AF in patients suffering from TIA in accordance with tissue-based definition, and the findings may have direct implications for physicians treating patients with cerebrovascular events.

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